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Research Article

**RATE OF OCCURRENCE OF GALLSTONES AMONG
PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM CHRONIC LIVER DISEASES**¹Dr Shahzeen Eisha, ²Dr Rabail Naseer, ³Dr Hafiz Muhammad Bilal¹Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to find out the rate of occurrence of complication of gallstone in the patients suffering from chronic liver diseases in Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.

Study Design: This was a transverse research work.

Study Setting: This study was carried out on those patients who got admission in the Medical ward of Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.

Study Subjects: Total 100 patients suffering from cirrhosis from any age or gender who appeared with the signs of chronic diseases of liver were the part of this research work. The main outcome measure was the presence of the gallstones.

Results: Among total one hundred patients, fifty patients were male & fifty patients were from female gender in the range of age from thirty to seventy years with an average age of 45 ± 11 years. Among total patients 31.0% patients were available with gallstones. Among these, 17 out of 50 (34.0%) patients were females & 14 out of 50 (28.0%) patients were from male gender. There was also availability of the related oedema of wall of gallbladder. There were 30 patients among 100 who were reactive for HbsAg, 70 patients out of one hundred were anti-hepatitis C reactive & ten patients were available as positive for both HbsAg as well as anti-HCV. We found the 70.0% patients in the child criteria B of the Pugh's modification & 30.0% patients were in the standard C and we found no patient in the Class-A.

Conclusion: The occurrence of the gallstones is very common in the patients suffering from the chronic diseases of liver. There is not any impact on the rate of survival due to them and majority of the patients came to know about the complication during interrogation accidentally. The very effectual non-invasive method for this investigation is ultrasonography.

Keywords: Chronic, Ultrasonography, Interrogation, Hepatitis, Positive, Gallstone, Effectual, Impact, Gallbladder, Occurrence.

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INTRODUCTION:

The liver cirrhosis is an important reason of morbidity as well as mortality among population of Pakistan, most frequent result of the HCV infection in comparison to wine usage in the countries of west. The infections because of HCV are very frequent in comparison with the infection of HBV in the population of our country Pakistan [1, 2], while the infection of both of these viruses can be the reason in the single patient. Since ultrasound invention, it is the matter of notification that the prevalence of gallstones is very frequent in the patients who are suffering from liver cirrhosis. The patients having the chronic liver diseases have a strong association with the presence of gallstones. Their rate of occurrence is four to five times greater than the normal healthy population & there is no any impact of the gallstones on the rate of survival [3]. There are different types of stones as pigment, cholesterol & mixed. Stones of cholesterol are normally single while the pigment & mixed stones are available in multiple condition.

There are various reasons for the prevalence of these stones. Metabolic defects can be accountable for various kinds of the stones. The amount of the salt of bile decreases in the bile with the increased level of the estrogens & aspects which interfere with enterohepatic circulation of the salts of bile. The main question is that what is accountable for the cirrhosis gallbladder of liver? Perhaps both are responsible for this complication in fact as there is a decrease in the contractility of the gall bladder, there is reduction in the bile acid pool [4], increased conversion of cholic acid into the deoxy-cholic acid so there is replacement of the cholic acid with increased concentration of the deoxycholic acid & it may lead to the formation of abnormal vesicle, there is high concentration of the cholesterol in these vesicles and aggregates into the big multi-lamellar vesicles [5]. Majority of patients with chronic liver diseases were not aware about the presence of gallstones.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work carried out on 100 patients in which 50 were males & 50 were from female gender

with positive history of the chronic diseases of liver who appeared in the emergency OPD of the Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan from January 2018 to December 2018 for a period of one year. Thorough examination of all the patients carried out & we confirmed the presence of liver cirrhosis in those patients. Examination of complete blood cells, assessment of urine, tests for the check of liver function, gastroscopy & ultrasound of the abdomen carried out. The patients who were not suffering from the liver cirrhosis were not the part of this research work. We did not perform the liver biopsy for any patient. Ultrasonography carried out for all the patients of this research work, as the main aim was to find out the rate of occurrence of presence of gallstones in those patients. There were 3 different identification of ultrasound in the identification of the gallbladder:

1. One or greater than one echogenic, distally shadowing probable mobile structures inside the gallbladder.
2. One or higher than one echogenic, mobile but not shadowing constructions inside the gallbladder.
3. Echogenic construction with consistent shadowing in the area of the fossa of gall-bladder with a lit bit visualization of gallbladder.

RESULTS:

The mean age of these patients was 45 ± 11 years with arrange of 30 to 70 year of age and we found 31.0% patients suffering from the complication of gallstone. It is appropriate to record that this was greatly selective patients group who appeared in this very hospital. Total 17 out of 50 (34.0%) females were present with anomaly of gallstones while 14 out of fifty (28.0%) were the male patients appeared with gallstones. We found no important disparity in the gender distribution of the disease. Among these 17 females, thirteen females found with a single stone & four females were available with more than one stone. In the same manner, twelve out of fourteen males were present with single stone & two patients were available with more than one stone.

Table I: Demographic Data (n = 100)

Characteristics	Values
Total patients	100.0
M : F	1:01
Age range	30 to 70 years
Mean Age	45
Positive for gall stones	31.0
Males (n=50)	14.0
Females (n=50)	17.0
Anti HCV positive	70.0
HBsAg	30.0
Both (B+C) positive	10.0

Approximately all the patients of this research work were available with oedema in the wall of gall bladder, which was much noticeable among the patients suffering from serious nature intractable ascites. Total 30 patients were available as reactive to HbsAg & seventy patients were anti-hepatitis C reactive while ten patients were positive for both HbsAg & anti-hepatitis C reactive. About 30.0% patients came under the classification of the in child standard C of the Pugh's modification while 70.0% patients were present in Class-B & there was no patient in the Class-A.

DISCUSSION:

Liver cirrhosis is very serious issue of health and it is the reason of high amount of morbidity as well as mortality in our country Pakistan. The average of the patients was much similar with one other research work conducted in the same city [1]. In this research work, 31.0% patients were available with gallstones, and there was no impact of this complication on patients. Although this prevalence is very high but it is

vital to keep in mind that this contains highly selective populace but still this can be in comparison with the Conte De [6] & Elzouki [7] who concluded that 29.50% & 30.0% patients with cirrhosis were available with gallstones. Maggi A [8] & Chung Pi Si [9] had displayed a high rate of occurrence in 38.0% & 41.0% patients of cirrhosis having gallstones.

Sheen [10] concluded that there were 18.50% males & 31.20% females found with gallstones among patients with cirrhosis. Razi [11]. Concluded the occurrence of the gallstones as 15.0% in populace of Pakistan which is less than the occurrence in the patients with cirrhosis. Some of the factors for high occurrence are use of alcohol [12], hemolysis's lithogeny role [13], less discharge of cholesterol & reduced pool of the bile acid [14]. The abnormal gallbladder is also the possible risk factor for the formation of the gallstones [15]. Fornari [16] in his research work states that high estrogen's & progesterone levels are the reason of stasis of gall bladder. Autonomous neuropathy [17] is very frequent among the patients suffering from the

chronic diseases of liver regardless of the reasons behind the reasons of the disease of liver. Chawla A [18] also stated that autonomous neuropathy can play its part for the gallstone formation. Acalovschi M [19] & Kao CH [20] were also in favor of contractibility of the gallbladder in patients of cirrhosis while Chung Pin [8] & Pompili [21] were not agree from this view. The extremity of the diseases of liver [22, 23] are important risk factors for cirrhotic patients. Different research works have displayed the anti-hepatitis C virus reactive in the range changing from 18.0% [24], 37.50% [25], 62.20% [26] & 65.50% [1] among the patients suffering from cirrhosis & both were reactive in 24.40% [1].

CONCLUSION:

The complication of gallstones is very common among patients suffering from chronic diseases of liver. They have no impact on the survival rate & majority of the patients know it occasionally when they come under investigation, an excellent non-invasive method for the investigation of this complication is ultrasonography.

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